

Cyclic Voltammetry of Thallium(I) in Different Supporting Electrolytes

R. S. SINDAL, K. C. K. MATHUR and R. C. KAPOOR

Department of Chemistry, University of Jodhpur, Jodhpur-342 001

The reduction of Tl(I) has been made in presence of various sodium salts as supporting electrolytes at a hanging mercury drop electrode (HMDE). The correlation of cathodic and anodic peak currents and the difference in cathodic and anodic peak potentials with the voltage scan rates indicate that the reduction of Tl(I) is not reversible.

WITH the help of the theory of stationary electrode voltammetry proposed by Nicholson and Shain¹, it is possible to develop diagnostic criteria by correlating kinetic and experimental parameters so that unknown system can be characterized by studying the variations of peak current, half-peak potential, or ratio of anodic to cathodic peak currents as a function of rate of voltage scan.

For a reversible system the separation of peak anodic and cathodic potentials of the couple² is $\frac{58}{n}$ mv and to a good approximation the formal electrode potential can be computed by averaging the two peak potentials. However, the peak to peak distance is larger for an irreversible system³.

The effect of a chemical reaction on the voltammetric wave will depend on its rate, as compared with the time required to perform the experiment. Taking irreversible succeeding chemical reaction as an example, if a very rapid reaction is studied with very slow scan rates, the stationary electrode voltammogram will reflect the characteristics of the chemical step almost entirely. On the other hand, if the rate of voltage scan is rapid compared to the rate of the reaction, the curves are identical to those for the corresponding uncomplicated charge transfer reactions. Hence in every kinetic case, the ratio of the rate constant to the rate of voltage scan appears in the kinetic parameter. This, in turn, makes it possible to use these relations to define diagnostic criteria for the investigation of unknown systems.

The relationship between scan rate (V) and I_{pa}/I_{pc} or $I_{pc}/V^{1/2}$ is often used as a diagnostic criteria for identifying the nature of the electrode process. Here I_{pa} and I_{pc} are anodic and cathodic peak currents in a cyclic voltammogram.

The authors have used these criteria to investigate the reduction of Tl(I) in different supporting electrolytes.

Experimental

Cyclic voltammograph CV-1, (Bioanalytical System Inc., U.S.A.), in combination with an X-Y recorder (Digilog) was used to record the cyclic voltammograms.

A special cell having three-electrode assembly was used. Hanging mercury drop electrode (HMDE)⁴⁻⁷ was used as the working electrode while a platinum spiral was employed as the auxiliary electrode. All potentials were measured against a saturated calomel electrode (SCE) which was connected to the test solution through a sodium nitrate bridge. All experiments were carried out at $35 \pm 0.1^\circ$ by immersing the cell and the reference electrode in a cryostat, type MK-70 (Web Mlw Prufgerate Werk, GDR).

Reagent grade chemicals were used in all the experiments. The concentration of Tl(I) ion was kept at $5 \times 10^{-4} M$, while the supporting electrolytes used were NaNO_3 , NaClO_4 , NaCl and Na_2SO_4 .

Cyclic voltammograms were taken at different scan rates varying from 0.02 to 0.1 volt/sec. The

TABLE 1—POTENTIAL VALUES OF Tl⁺ IN DIFFERENT SUPPORTING ELECTROLYTES (IN VOLTS VS SCE)

Sl. No.	Scan rate Volts/sec.	0.1 M NaNO ₃			0.1 M NaCl			0.1 M NaClO ₄			0.1 M Na ₂ SO ₄		
		E _{pa}	E _{pc}	ΔE _p	E _{pa}	E _{pc}	ΔE _p	E _{pa}	E _{pc}	ΔE _p	E _{pa}	E _{pc}	ΔE _p
1.	0.02	-0.47	-0.55	0.08	-0.48	-0.56	0.08	-0.47	-0.55	0.08	-0.49	-0.57	0.08
2.	0.03	-0.47	-0.55	0.08	-0.48	-0.55	0.07	-0.47	-0.55	0.08	-0.49	-0.57	0.08
3.	0.04	-0.47	-0.55	0.08	-0.47	-0.55	0.08	-0.47	-0.55	0.08	-0.49	-0.57	0.08
4.	0.05	-0.46	-0.55	0.09	-0.47	-0.55	0.08	-0.47	-0.54	0.07	-0.49	-0.57	0.08
5.	0.06	-0.46	-0.55	0.09	-0.47	-0.55	0.08	-0.47	-0.55	0.08	-0.48	-0.56	0.08
6.	0.07	-0.46	-0.55	0.09	-0.47	-0.55	0.08	-0.46	-0.54	0.08	-0.49	-0.57	0.08
7.	0.08	-0.46	-0.56	0.10	-0.47	-0.54	0.08	-0.47	-0.55	0.08	-0.49	-0.57	0.08
8.	0.09	-0.46	-0.56	0.10	-0.47	-0.55	0.08	-0.46	-0.55	0.09	-0.48	-0.56	0.08
9.	0.10	-0.45	-0.55	0.10	-0.46	-0.54	0.08	-0.46	-0.54	0.08	-0.49	-0.57	0.08

TABLE 2—VALUES OF CATHODIC AND ANODIC PEAK CURRENTS IN MICROAMPERES

Sl. No.	Scan rate Volts/sec.	0.1 M NaNO ₃			0.1 M NaCl			0.1 M NaClO ₄			0.1 M Na ₂ SO ₄		
		I _{pa}	I _{pc}	I _{pa} /I _{pc}	I _{pa}	I _{pc}	I _{pa} /I _{pc}	I _{pa}	I _{pc}	I _{pa} /I _{pc}	I _{pa}	I _{pc}	I _{pa} /I _{pc}
1.	0.02	5.05	2.45	2.06	4.75	2.0	2.38	4.50	1.85	2.43	2.6	1.5	1.73
2.	0.03	5.6	3.4	1.64	5.0	2.8	1.79	4.7	2.65	1.74	3.05	1.9	1.6
3.	0.04	6.05	3.95	1.53	5.3	3.25	1.63	5.05	2.8	1.8	3.3	2.2	1.5
4.	0.05	6.0	4.05	1.48	5.45	3.45	1.58	5.05	3.3	1.53	3.5	2.5	1.4
5.	0.06	6.4	4.3	1.49	5.5	3.7	1.49	5.25	3.65	1.44	3.35	2.65	1.26
6.	0.07	6.75	4.95	1.57	5.75	4.05	1.42	5.65	4.0	1.41	3.85	2.8	1.37
7.	0.08	6.85	4.5	1.52	5.55	3.85	1.44	5.3	3.85	1.38	4.0	3.0	1.33
8.	0.09	7.5	5.4	1.5	5.90	4.35	1.36	5.8	4.35	1.33	4.1	3.25	1.26
9.	0.10	8.05	5.75	1.4	6.1	4.5	1.36	5.8	4.3	1.35	4.2	3.4	1.24

Fig. 1. Plot of I_{pa}/I_{pc} vs scan rate (V) in different supporting electrolytes: (I) 0.1M NaClO₄; (II) 0.1M NaCl; (III) 0.1M NaNO₃; (IV) 0.1M Na₂SO₄.

Fig. 2. Plot of I_{pa}/V^{1/2} vs scan rate (V) in different supporting electrolytes: (I) 0.1M NaNO₃; (II) 0.1M NaCl; (III) 0.1M NaClO₄; (IV) 0.1M Na₂SO₄.

starting and returning potentials were -0.2 and -1.0 volt, respectively.

Results and Discussion

The anodic and cathodic peak potentials (E_{pa} and E_{pc}) and peaks potential differences (ΔE_p) were calculated from the cyclic voltammograms obtained in different supporting electrolytes (Table 1).

One of the criteria for reversibility is that $\Delta E_p = \frac{58}{n}$ mv. It is clear from Table 1 that the reduction of Tl(I) is not reversible in any of the supporting electrolytes, since $\Delta E_p \approx 0.08$ volt in all the cases. It is further noted that ΔE_p remains unchanged on increasing the scan rate. However, the values of E_{pa} and E_{pc} are more negative in 0.1M Na₂SO₄ supporting electrolyte.

The cathodic and anodic peak currents were measured at different scan rates for various supporting electrolytes. Results are given in Table 2 in which the values of I_{pa}/I_{pc} are also recorded. It is seen that the ratio I_{pa}/I_{pc} is not unity in any case. On increasing the scan rate, the ratio decreases regularly due to the fact that the cathodic peak current is enhanced at high scan rates. The plot of I_{pa}/I_{pc} vs V is shown in Fig. 1.

TABLE 3

Sl. No.	Scan rate Volts/sec V	0.1 M NaNO ₃ $I_{pc}/V^{1/2}$	0.1 M NaCl $I_{pc}/V^{1/2}$	0.1 M NaClO ₄ $I_{pc}/V^{1/2}$	0.1 M Na ₂ SO ₄ $I_{pc}/V^{1/2}$
1.	0.02	17.4	14.2	13.1	10.6
2.	0.03	19.7	16.2	15.3	11.0
3.	0.04	19.8	16.3	14.0	11.0
4.	0.05	18.1	15.4	14.7	11.2
5.	0.06	17.6	15.1	14.9	10.8
6.	0.07	18.7	15.3	15.1	10.6
7.	0.08	15.9	13.6	18.7	10.6
8.	0.09	18.0	14.5	19.3	10.8
9.	0.10	18.2	14.2	18.4	10.8

The ratios of cathodic peak current and square root of scan rate, for different supporting electrolytes, are given in Table 3. The plots of $I_{pc}/V^{1/2}$ vs V

for all the supporting electrolytes are given in Fig. 2. The plots yield almost horizontal lines.

All the above mentioned data indicate conclusively that the reduction of Tl(I) in the supporting electrolytes employed is not reversible at a mercury electrode. This conclusion appears contradictory to the accepted notion that the polarographic reduction of Tl(I) is reversible⁸. This clearly shows that the criteria of reversibility based on logarithmic plot analysis of polarographic curves is not reliable.

References

1. R. S. NICHOLSON and I. SHAIN, *Analytical Chemistry*, 1964, 36, 706.
2. R. N. ADAMS, "Electrochemistry at Solid Electrodes", Marcel Dekker, New York, N. Y., 1969, Chap. 5.
3. R. S. NICHOLSON, *Analytical Chemistry*, 1965, 37, 1351.
4. W. KEMULA and Z. KUBLIK, *Nature*, 1958, 182, 793.
5. W. KEMULA and Z. KUBLIK, *Roczniki Chem.*, 1958, 32, 941.
6. W. KEMULA, Z. R. GRABOWSKI and M. K. KALINOWSKI, *Naturwiss.*, 1960, 22, 1.
7. W. KEMULA, Z. KUBLIK and R. CYRANSKI, *Roczniki Chem.*, 1962, 36, 1339.
8. J. HEYROVSKY, "Principles of Polarography", Academic Press, New York, 1966, p. 129.